

ALGORITHM OF A MODIFIED THERAPEUTIC AND DIAGNOSTIC APPROACH IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF GALLSTONE DISEASE AFTER BARIATRIC SURGERY

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ABSTRACT

Despite the high effectiveness of surgical methods for the treatment of obesity, long-term postoperative complications often develop and require repeated interventions. One of the most common and clinically significant complications is gallstone disease (GSD), which develops against the background of rapid weight loss, impaired bile outflow, and changes in lipid metabolism. The incidence of GSD after bariatric surgery ranges from 25% to 50%, and in some patients the disease manifests as acute cholecystitis, choledocholithiasis, or pancreatitis, requiring emergency cholecystectomy or biliary drainage [2]. The relevance of this issue is determined by the need to develop reliable strategies for the prevention of GSD in this group of patients, taking into account the increasing number of bariatric surgeries and the younger age of the operated population.

Relevance. Despite the high effectiveness of surgical methods for the treatment of obesity, long-term postoperative complications often develop and require repeated interventions. One of the most common and clinically significant complications is gallstone disease (GSD), which develops against the background of rapid weight loss, impaired bile outflow, and changes in lipid metabolism. The incidence of GSD after bariatric surgery ranges from 25% to 50%, and in some patients the disease manifests as acute cholecystitis, choledocholithiasis, or pancreatitis, requiring emergency cholecystectomy or biliary drainage [2]. The relevance of this issue is determined by the need to develop reliable strategies for the prevention of GSD in this group of patients, taking into account the increasing number of bariatric surgeries and the younger age of the operated population [1].

Aim of the study. To develop and implement a clinical model aimed at reducing the incidence of postoperative gallstone disease and the need for repeated surgical interventions in patients who have undergone bariatric surgery.

Materials and Methods. The present study was conducted at the private clinics Soglom Avlod and SEHAT in Andijan during the period from 2023 to 2025. A total of 1,337 bariatric surgeries were performed during this period, including laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG)

and one-anastomosis gastric bypass (OAGB), for the treatment of obesity and obesity combined with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM).

Among the 1,337 patients, 102 (7.6%) subsequently developed gallstone disease (GSD) after bariatric surgery. Repeat cholecystectomy was performed in 51 (3.8%) patients, who constituted the core group for risk factor analysis. Accordingly, the study population comprised 102 (7.6%) patients with postoperative GSD. Two groups were conditionally defined in the study:

- **Comparison group** (2023) – 483 patients. GSD subsequently developed in 44 (9.1%) patients, of whom 32 (6.6%) required repeat surgical interventions.

- **Main group** (2024–2025) – 854 patients. GSD subsequently developed in 58 (6.8%) patients, of whom 19 (2.2%) required repeat surgical interventions.

In the comparison group, 2 (6.3%) surgeries required extension of the surgical approach, whereas no conversions were recorded in the main group, indicating the technical safety of the proposed algorithm. A reduction in mean blood loss was observed from 90 mL in the comparison group to 35 mL in the main group, which ensured lower surgical trauma and reduced the risk of postoperative complications. The length of hospital stay in the main group averaged 2.8 days compared to 5.6 days in the comparison group—almost twofold shorter—reflecting a faster postoperative recovery and the absence of complications. Postoperative complications were observed only in the comparison group in 4 (12.5%) patients.

To address the study objectives, clinical, laboratory, instrumental, and statistical research methods were applied in accordance with the latest standard methodologies and the examination guidelines approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results of the study. According to the modified therapeutic and diagnostic algorithm, the aim of the developed approach was to establish a decision-making system for performing simultaneous cholecystectomy during bariatric surgery in obese patients, based on a prognostic preoperative assessment of risk factors, including type 2 diabetes mellitus, hepatic steatosis, body mass index, the presence of biliary sludge, and morphological changes of the gallbladder. The algorithm is based on a combination of clinical and metabolic patient characteristics and gallbladder morphological changes detected by ultrasonography.

In the comparison group, 2 (6.3%) surgeries required extension of the surgical approach, whereas no conversions were recorded in the main group, indicating the technical safety of the proposed algorithm. A reduction in mean blood loss was observed from 90 mL in the comparison group to 35 mL in the main group, which ensured lower surgical trauma and reduced the risk of postoperative complications. The length of hospital stay in the main group averaged 2.8 days compared to 5.6 days in the comparison group—almost twofold shorter—reflecting a faster postoperative recovery and the absence of complications. Postoperative complications were observed only in the comparison group in 4 (12.5%) patients.

Consideration of clinical and metabolic risk factors is of paramount importance, including the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus, the severity of hepatic steatosis, body mass index, as well as medical history data indicating biliary sludge or dyskinesia. The presence of two or more unfavorable factors significantly increases the likelihood of gallbladder-related complications and constitutes an indication for simultaneous cholecystectomy. A particularly

high-risk group includes patients with long-standing or unstable type 2 diabetes mellitus, as well as those in whom dense pericholecystic adhesions are identified intraoperatively.

In the absence of structural changes or high-risk features, it is reasonable to limit the intervention to bariatric surgery alone. However, in such cases, mandatory administration of ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) at a dose of 10–15 mg/kg/day is recommended. The duration of prophylactic therapy should be at least 6 months, and in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and an intermediate level of risk, up to 12 months with individualized dose adjustment. In cases of simultaneous cholecystectomy, UDCA is prescribed for a minimum of 3–6 months.

Postoperative follow-up includes regular ultrasound monitoring of the biliary system at 3, 6, and 12 months, as well as biochemical liver function tests performed at the same intervals. Subsequently, patients remain under dispensary observation for up to 3 years, which allows timely detection of late complications and adjustment of therapy. If patients who have undergone bariatric surgery without cholecystectomy develop signs of biliary sludge, pain syndrome, or structural changes of the gallbladder during follow-up, elective cholecystectomy is considered a justified management strategy.

Thus, the modified therapeutic and diagnostic algorithm made it possible to reduce the incidence of gallstone disease (9.1% vs. 6.8%, respectively; a 1.3-fold reduction) and the rate of repeat surgical interventions (6.6% vs. 2.2%, respectively; a threefold reduction). Prolonged administration of ursodeoxycholic acid (≥ 6 months) was found to be safe and effective, particularly in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Conclusion. Therefore, the expanded indications for cholecystectomy are justified and should be incorporated into the standard preoperative assessment. Complicated forms of gallstone disease were identified exclusively in the comparison group. Repeat surgeries in the main group were short, safe, and not associated with complications. The proposed algorithm increases patient satisfaction, reduces postoperative complaints and repeat hospital visits, and ensures cost-effectiveness. In this regard, the modified algorithm represents a clinically justified, safe, effective, and economically sound approach to optimizing surgical strategy in bariatric practice, especially in patients with obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus

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